

A COLD CASE IN THE EARLY ELECTROACOUSTIC MUSIC REPERTOIRE: THE ‘GLISSANDO SWARMS’ OF *DIAMORPHOSES*

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Abstract

The first tape music composed by Iannis Xenakis, *Diamorphoses* (GRM Paris, 1957) features extremely peculiar sonorities that challenge and even resist clear qualitative descriptions, making it difficult or impossible to ground music analysis on shared notions of the ‘sound object’, as worked out by scholars in the shade of Pierre Schaeffer’s early contributions.

Few sources are available about its actual production in the studio. They often mention the use of magnetophonic prototypes developed at GRM, the *phonogène* and the *morphophone*. There is little doubt the former was really used. In contrast, mention of the morphophone has always remained highly problematic. No specimens of that device have survived their times and the few indicators about its use in actual compositional work are largely conjectural.

For these reasons, *Diamorphoses* is a kind of ‘cold case’ in the history of early electroacoustic music: some of its most remarkable sonorities are poorly understood partly because the studio production strategies devised to create them are poorly documented. We make the hypothesis that the morphophone was indeed utilized by Xenakis to create the unique textural sonorities heard in later passages of *Diamorphoses*, described as “layered swarms of glissando” in [Frisius 2009, 147-148]. For our discussion to lay on empirical grounds, we try to model or reconstruct the operations the composer might have gone through to create such sonorities. We can make such an attempt thanks to the DIGITAL MORPHOPHONE ENVIRONMENT, a recent MaxMSP application meant to replicate (and eventually extend) the morphophone functionalities in the digital domain.

Our tests ultimately provide indirect but reliable empirical evidence that those layered streams of glissandoing sounds were indeed the outcome of analog signal processing operations that could only be pursued with the morphophone, in the GRM studio as of 1957. Accordingly, the conjecture that Xenakis had used the morphophone in the realization of *Diamorphoses* can be considered correct. We also suggest that, by employing that device in special manners, he might have tried to somehow measure or at least grade the sonic density of his thick sonic textures.

1. Introduction

The study of the pioneering electroacoustic repertoire (1950s—1970s) typically requires renewed conceptual perspectives and analytical tools, of a kind hopefully fruitful when also

investigating other creative musical practices in the larger scenario of the modern and contemporary media arts. Especially relevant should be considered the need to develop an appropriate insight into the actual productive practices involved in creative work, which is often hampered by the central role that must be necessarily assigned to technical apparatuses by now long obsolete.

In the following, we consider the case of *Diamorphoses*, the first tape music work composed by Iannis Xenakis. It features some extremely peculiar sonorities, largely irreducible to shared descriptions and resistant to notions of the ‘sound object’ laying at the core of much electroacoustic music studies since Pierre Schaeffer’s early theoretical contributions [Schaeffer 1966]. A general approach of ‘analysis by listening’ should be integrated with ‘analysis by doing’: in our view, a purely ‘aesthetic’ perspective should leave way to, or at least absorb, knowledge emerging in a ‘poietic’ perspective (to borrow the Jean-Jacques Nattiez well-known terminology [Nattiez 1990]).

1.1. Xenakis’s *Diamorphoses* in context

Iannis Xenakis (1922-2001) composed *Diamorphoses* in 1957, in the studios of the *Groupe de Recherche de Musique Concrète* established by Pierre Schaeffer (renamed *Groupe de Recherches Musicales*, GRM, in 1958). This was his first endeavor in electroacoustic music. The work premiered on October 5th, 1958 in Brussels (GRM concert at Expo 1958). Olivier Messiaen expressed his admiration [Messiaen 1959]. François Bernard Mâche would later describe it as “a work of musique concrète that finally surpassed the experimental level” [Mâche 2000, 153]¹. *Diamorphoses* is no doubt a milestone in the early electroacoustic repertoire, but it is also a very peculiar example of musique concrète, not exactly conformant to the guidelines generally followed at the GRM in those years.

At that time, Xenakis was genuinely interested in Schaeffer’s descriptive notions of different typologies and morphologies of sound. As a composer, he was interested in the possibility of shaping the dynamic timbral morphology of sound materials. As is known, the title *Diamorphoses* (ancient Greek *δια-μορφοσις*) may be understood as ‘formations’ or ‘transformations’ (of sound) according to criteria of continuity (gradual change) and discontinuity (sudden change) [Delalande 1997, 160]. As he entered the GRM studio, the young Xenakis also hoped to expand the probabilistic compositional mechanisms he had been developing in earlier orchestral works (*Pithoprakta*, 1956; *Achorripsis*, 1957).

Over the decades, various authors have analyzed *Diamorphoses* based on their subjective listening, and occasionally integrated such an approach with shared (intersubjective) perceptual criteria and graphic transcriptions [Solomos 1993, De Stefano 1998, DeLio 2002, Frisius 2009, Solomos 2011, Solomos & Gibson 2013]. Others have made recourse to signal analysis strategies based on feature-extraction methods and perceptually relevant descriptors [Malt 2015]. Information emerging from the composer’s archives was also relevant for analytical observations [Solomos 2011, Solomos & Gibson 2013]. All authors remark the various categories of sound materials, also including environmental sound materials (e.g., earthquake rumblings, thunders, bomb explosions...) taken from sound archives accessible at the GRM at the time of composing. They all divide the full duration of the piece

¹ Here and below, the translation of all French quotes is provided by the authors of the present paper.

(approximately 6'55") into three main parts, with perhaps significant differences in the timing of the middle part. It should be noted, however, that Xenakis seemed to rather suggest that *Diamorphoses* divides into two main parts [Delalande 1997, 39].

1.2. Magnetophonic devices

Available information on the production process of *Diamorphoses* is scarce, summary and uncertain. Apart from the ordinary magnetic tape editing and mixing operations, some authors [Solomos & Gibson 2013, Solomos 2011, Friedl 2019] mention the use of the *phonogène* and *morphophone*, magnetic tape based devices designed by Schaeffer and Jacques Poullin in the early 1950s. Today, those systems have long since been lost, if not even destroyed [Teruggi 2001].

That Xenakis might have used the *phonogène à coulisse* — which allowed for the rotation speed of a tape recorder to be varied continuously, resulting in a smooth time scaling of the signal (hence in proportional changes in frequency and duration) — seems plausible and is even taken for granted in [Battier 2001]. It must have represented for the composer a simple way to impose a glissando curve to any sound material (including the small bell sound heard at several spots across the first half of the piece). Equally plausible is the use of the *phonogène chromatique* or *phonogène à clavier* ('keyboard phonogène', for discrete pitch shifts along a regular twelve-tone scale, across two octaves). Both phonogènes were regularly used by the GRM composers in the 1950s.

More problematic is the issue of the morphophone, a device developed since 1953 [Teruggi 2007, Gayou 2007] and often included among the most innovative sound processing devices of the time [Poullin 1954, unknown 1960, Ussachevsky 1968, Cross 1968]. In actuality, there seems to be no certainty about its use in GRM musical productions as a whole. Daniel Teruggi (head of GRM 1997–2017) suggests that the morphophone was probably utilised in the late 1950s in the production of works by composers Luc Ferrari and André Boucourechliev². Other sources assume that Schaeffer and Pierre Henry had already used it for *Orphée 1953* (for three voices, harpsichord, violin, and tape, 1953) [Brech 2009, Fox 2005]. However, similar indications are not supported by documentary evidence. In a paper bearing on the technical developments at the GRM, Teruggi even doubts that the device was ever in use in relevant musical productions [Teruggi 2007]. It should be noted that Xenakis never mentioned the morphophone, neither in writings nor interviews, not even when commenting on *Diamorphoses*. Not even Schaeffer's major publications about musique concrète ever mentioned it! [Schaeffer 1966, Schaeffer 1967].

It seems that the morphophone was afflicted by technical problems and various malfunctions that eventually discouraged musicians from using it [Teruggi 2007, 230]. That ties in well with the circumstance that Francis Coupigny (Poullin's assistant, at that time) designed and built a new one, in 1960, presumably more reliable and performant than the earlier prototype [Coupigny 2001]³. In any case, in agreement with Teruggi, it is safe to say that the signal processing techniques offered by this device became of ordinary use for GRM composers

² Daniel Teruggi, personal email, May 7, 2021.

³ In [Friedl 2019] it is suggested, somewhat in passing, that the 1960 morphophone was used by Xenakis in 1962 for *Bohor*.

only in much later years, namely in the late 1990s (with software resources such as GRM Tools [Favreau 1998, Teruggi & Geslin 2004]).

In a way, *Diamorphoses* represents a ‘cold case’ in the history of early electroacoustic music: as illustrated below, some of the most remarkable sonorities it features are poorly understood and the studio production strategies devised to create them have never been carefully documented.

1.3. A short introduction to the morphophone

The morphophone included a tape loop (approximately 4 seconds long, at a standard speed of 38 cm/sec) mounted on a rotating wheel mechanism, with a recording head and an erasing head in fixed positions and ten playback heads to be shifted and repositioned along the wheel circumference (within physical constraints). Each playback head signal passed through a bandpass filter before being amplified and finally summed up to the other playback head signals. Playback head signals could be also sent back to the recording head, resulting in a feedback system configuration. Removing the eraser head eventually resulted in a continuing process of re-recording and signal accumulation (overdub).

The sound to be processed was either pre-recorded on the loop, prior to any morphophone operation, or was provided from other sources in the studio (microphones, tape machines, or else).

We can see it as an extended sort of multi-tap delay system, of use for echo and reverberation effects. In the late 1950s, it could be likened to the *delay wheel* developed at the Philips Research Laboratories, in Eindhoven. A comparison between the two was made as early as 1958, namely in [Ussachevsky 1958]. We should observe, however, that the Philips delay wheel had been designed as a device integral to multi-channel sound diffusion systems, for ‘ambiophonic’ sound diffusion [Vermeulen 1958].

In the GRM environment, the morphophone was actually meant to provide not only or not so much echo and reverberation effects, but to “forge the dynamic profile of a sound object through the controlled repetition of a recorded cell” [unknown 1960, 122] and accordingly to achieve the “transformation of the morphology of sound through multiplication” [Ina-GRM 1980, 275; Chion & Reibel 1976, 225]. Thus characterised, it may have certainly captured Xenakis’s attention.

1.4. Questions

But for what purpose would Xenakis use the morphophone, in the frame of his very first creative approach on the tape medium? In the realization of what kind of sound material?

In order to answer that, we try to single out – through careful listening and based on a general knowledge of the electroacoustic studio practice of those early days – specific sound segments of *Diamorphoses* and to model or even reconstruct them with today’s technical resources. This amounts to trying to somehow replicate the operations that the composer might have carried out.

To that aim, in the following we outline some useful practical criteria and then proceed with some empirical signal processing tests. We take advantage of the DIGITAL MORPHOPHONE

ENVIRONMENT (DME), a software tool that models and replicates the functioning of the morphophone [Scorranese 2024, Scorranese 2025]. The basic goal is to reconstruct or at least mimic, surely with inevitable approximations, some of the peculiar sonorities heard in *Diamorphoses*.

2. Investigation criteria

2.1. Swarms and glissando spiderwebs

Given the functions attributed to the morphophone in the GRM historical and technical context, and considering Xenakis's interest for sound textures of high statistical 'density' (average quantity of unit events in a given time and frequency range), we focus on the sound complexes heard at later spots in the piece⁴. These include sounds heard in the segment from 2'22" to 4'05", and particularly an irregularly (aperiodically) repeated sound, slightly modulated in frequency, heard as the ringing of a very small metal object being repeatedly hit, whose spectral energy peaks at around 8.2 kHz (Figure 1).

Then, and perhaps more crucially, we should consider the segment from 4'10" to 6'55" (middle and final part of the piece), featuring webs of countless short glissandoing sounds, with spectral energy mostly concentrated in high frequency ranges: 1-7 kHz, 1-12.5 kHz, 4-12.5 kHz, 6-12.5 kHz, 7.5-10 kHz. Figure 2 shows the sonogram of some of these sound materials, in the order by which they appear in the piece, but isolated from concomitant sounds and abstracted from actual timing. It is very likely that composer Olivier Messiaen was referring to such peculiar sonorities when, after listening to *Diamorphoses*, he spoke of "gigantic and multicoloured sound spiderwebs" [Messiaen 1959, 5]. These were later called "layered swarms of glissandos" (geschichtete Glissandoschwärmen [Frisius 2009, 147-148]), "glissando masses" (Glissandomassen [Brech 2009, 48]) "masses of high-pitched glissando sounds" [Solomos 2002, 6], "glissando bands" [DeLio 2002, 50] and "thicker strands of [...] glissando sounds" [Di Scipio 2015, 380]. To a greater extent than other sound materials, these "clustered glissandos" [Brech 2009, 45] mark indelibly the complete *Diamorphoses*.

2.2. Studio work

2.2.1. Building block and multi-layering

In the 1990s, Xenakis recalled that those passages of *Diamorphoses* were thoroughly crafted and that he had used the sound of a small bell as the minimal building block to work them out [Delalande 1997, 39]. However, he never clarified how he actually proceeded. It seems likely that he used first the phonogène à coulisse, in order to impose a glissando curve on the bell

⁴ For reference, we have at our disposal one of the available compact disc recordings of *Diamorphoses*, namely EMF-003, 1997. According to the CD booklet, *Diamorphoses* is a 'mono' tape composition, even though the actual audio track presents slight but non-negligible differences between the two channels. Indeed, there is little consensus on the actual number of tape channels, for reasons we can't discuss here. Sources vary in defining this work as 'mono', 'stereo' and even 'four-track' [Friedl 2015, Matossian 1981]. In the present paper, we follow the current official catalogue of Xenakis's works [Xenakis Catalogue 2001], where *Diamorphoses* is denoted as a stereo tape piece. See also [Di Scipio & Solomos 2025].

sound, as suggested in [Battier 2001]. It seems also likely, we suggest, that he then used the morphophone to ‘multiply’ that unit element, i.e. to repeat it in as large quantities as to eventually produce a prolonged and thicker sound texture. Our suggestion seems consistent with some passing annotations made in [Brech 2009, Fried 2019]. In essence, resorting to the morphophone might have been a quicker way to achieve results equivalent to the layering of a large amount of tapes (with each tape having similar but not identical sound material). Xenakis himself seems to allude to the latter procedure in a passage from [Varga 1996, 111].

Figure 1. *Diamorphoses*. Tiny metallic object (‘small bell’) repeatedly hit at 2’22” (leftmost) and at other times, until 4’05” (rightmost).

Figure 2. *Diamorphoses*. “Glissando swarms” (excerpts). From left to right: 4’11”-4’23”, 4’35”-4’38”, 6’00”-6’12”, 6’35”-6’48”.

2.2.2. Density operator

In the second half of the 1950s, Xenakis became increasingly interested in determining the density of sound particles in larger constructs of texture-like auditory properties. Here, ‘density’ means average “number of events per second” [Varga 1996, 94]. It represented a novel compositional dimension, partly emerging already in some of Xenakis’s own (and others’s) coeval orchestral music. In those times, the perception of density in textural sound phenomena was a totally unexplored and perhaps even unknown issue in psychoacoustic research! Two years after *Diamorphoses*, working on *Analogique B* (a tape work initially conceived as a piece on its own right, then turned into the tape part in *Analogique A et B*, for nine string instruments and tape, 1958-59), Xenakis made considerable efforts in order to forge sound and music from innumerable ‘sound grains’, arranging them into ‘sound clouds’ of varying density [Di Scipio 2006, Di Scipio 2015]. In that context, he tried to regulate the perceived density of his sound clouds along a logarithmic scale with base 3. In other words, for a minimally relevant increase of density to be perceived, he had to triple the actual amount of grains [Varga 1996, 111; Di Scipio 2015].

A little later, Xenakis observed that he had arrived at that already in 1957, while in fact composing *Diamorphoses*, when he provisionally established that the perception of density follows “a logarithmic law with base between 2 and 3” [Xenakis 1963, 69]. Solomos [2011] suggests that the composer came to that insight through discussions with Abraham Moles (one of Schaeffer’s closest collaborators and a direct contributor to the design of the 1953 morphophone). Based on Xenakis’s handwritten annotations from those years, Barthel-Calvet [2022, 141] provides evidence that the composer even tried some experiments in the perception of density, involving his GRM mates, in July 1957, few months after starting work on *Diamorphoses*.

Following such observations, we should perhaps also consider that the morphophone appeared to Xenakis not only as a tool that could turn small sonic elements into articulated and prolonged textures, but also as a device by which he could somehow manage textural density, at least approximately. Using the morphophone in feedback configurations (or with overdubbing) could be a way to go in that direction. For the time being, this secondary hypothesis remains conjectural, yet it might be confirmed or rejected as we go through the empirical tests described in later sections.

3. Tests with the DIGITAL MORPHOPHONE ENVIRONMENT

3.1. A short introduction to the DME

The DIGITAL MORPHOPHONE ENVIRONMENT (DME) is a software tool designed to reproduce the morphophone process in the digital audio domain [Scorrane 2024, Scorrane 2025]. Its development moved from a careful overview of the few relevant information available, including technical schemes and archive images (pictures and videos) beside published papers and interviews. The current implementation is written in MaxMSP 9.1.2⁵. Its main goal is to provide a generic working model of the morphophone signal flow and related functionalities.

⁵ <https://cycling74.com/products/max> (last accessed February 19th, 2026).

Using the DME one may choose between ‘philological’ and ‘extended’ modes of operation. While the former basically adheres to the morphophone signal flow, the latter exploits additional digital signal processing techniques, expanding the potential of the DME for live computer performance situations. The graphical interface acts as the main control panel (Figure 3). It provides access to the relevant control parameters as well as to the component modules internal to the complete implementation. For the purposes of the present paper, it seems sufficient to show the overall block diagram (Figure 4), including only the main stages in the complete signal process. For details, readers are kindly referred to [Scorrane 2025].

Figure 3. DIGITAL MORPHOPHONE ENVIRONMENT, main panel.

In an attempt at modelling the morphophone functionalities, aspects of the analog circuitry were also taken into account, however limited to a generic emulation of coherent analog processing behaviors. Any considerations on this particular topic are bound to remain largely conjectural, however, because no documentation seems to exist of the morphophone circuits, the particular tubes, and the particular magnetic tapes involved. The available literature on ‘virtual analog’ modeling of early tape machines can be helpful [Camras 1998, Arnardottir *et al.* 2008, Välimäki *et al.* 2011, Chowdury 2019] but is totally unrelated to the particular historico-technical context (i.e. Radio France, 1950s).

Figure 4. DIGITAL MORPHOPHONE ENVIRONMENT, general block diagram.

3.2. Test procedure

We now discuss three tests and related findings⁶. The test procedure is as follows: we first select a sound snippet in *Diamorphoses* that may serve as the building block of a more complex sound texture, copy it from the available compact disc recording (footnote 4) and then submit it to DME operations (philological mode). With that, we attempt to model or replicate the kind of ‘multiplicative’ process by means of which Xenakis might have shaped his sonic textures.

Across the complete test procedure, we avoid using the bandpass filters available in the signal processing flow. We also refrain from activating the tape flutter and analog preamp emulation.

Let’s recall that the dense sound textures targeted here, heard in later moments of *Diamorphoses*, provide auditory percepts of peculiar *statistical complexity* — a notion referred to the behaviour of any information source that cannot be characterized in terms of deterministic dynamics. Accordingly, our goal is not really to reconstruct the exact micro-organisation in the original sound signal, but only to approximate a global behavior sounding somewhat similar to the original sonic stream.

Across these tests, we make regular use of common sonogram software, which helps us to figure out to what extent the sound resultant of the DME operations match against the original sound textures.

3.2.1. Test 1

To start with, let’s focus on the sound segment from 3’37” to 4’06”, more particularly on a repeating percussive sound with spectral energy peaking at 8.2 kHz (Figure 1). As a plausible unit element, we select an isolated percussive event presented at 3’10”, resembling in fact a tiny metal object being hit (we can easily presume that the latter resulted from the frequency shifting of the sound of a small bell, with the keyboard phonogène). To model or replicate the complete segment under observation, the selected snippet should be first repeated at irregularly spaced times, then more rapidly and with increasingly longer overlaps between subsequent repeats.

Our very first test only aims at approximating the irregular repeats heard from 3’45” to 3’49” (ten repeats of the tiny bell). We take the average time interval between subsequent repeats in the original segment and use that as the average delay time for the DME playback heads. Because the local amplitude peaks in the original signal are never exactly identical, the gain of the DME playback heads was also randomly varied, but only slightly. Figure 5 shows the sonogram of the original sound sequence (top) and that of the sound sequence we obtained (bottom).

Let’s proceed and try matching the density increase featured in the subsegment from 3’49” to 4’06”. This time, as the building block we use the sound sequence resulting from the DME test just described: in other words, we reinject the DME’s previous output into its input. The delay times are again slightly varied. Upon listening, it turns out that a lesser number of active

⁶ Related material is available at https://github.com/danielscorrane/SCIAMIGLISSANDO_audioExamples (last accessed February 19th, 2026).

playback heads would better approximate the targeted sound density. For example, with five heads (five delay lines) the result sounds indeed closer to the original. Figure 6 shows the sonogram of the original subsegment (top) and that of our tentative reconstruction (bottom).

Figure 5. *Diamorphoses*, excerpt 3'45'' – 3'49'' (top: original, bottom: reconstruction).

Figure 6. *Diamorphoses*, excerpt 3'49'' – 4'06'' (top: original, bottom: reconstruction).

3.2.2. Test 2

Let's now consider the texture heard from 4'26'' to 4'49'', with spectral energy concentrated in the band 5.5-10 kHz. Featured here are a few abrupt interruptions, probably tape cuts resulting from further tape editing by Xenakis. Another, very similar texture is heard from 6'16'' to 6'44'', which features more gentle amplitude variations instead of sudden tape cuts. For simplicity, we prefer working on the latter one. Its sonogram is in Figure 7 (top). This texture probably expands a brief polyphonic interweaving of glissandoing sounds heard at 4'11'' (whose sonogram is the leftmost in Figure 2). In turn, the latter was arguably created by mixing various copies of the previously mentioned tiny bell sound, apparently modulated this time with the *phonogène à coulisse* (glissando). The two — the contrapuntal episode at 4'11'' and the textural stream starting at 6'16'' — share the same frequency range and the same energy distribution in that range, including a characteristic dip between 6 and 7 kHz. For our second test, therefore, we pick the former as the input unit element to the DME processing, in the attempt to model or reconstruct the latter.

We accordingly adjust the ten DME delay times in consideration of the much higher density of the textural segment under observation, and set all playback head levels to -6 dB. The resultant texture, however, does not sound enough dense, compared with the original. So we submit it to further DME processing, with ten new random delay times. The density now sounds closer to the original, or slightly greater perhaps. Figure 7 shows the sonogram of the

original (top) and our reconstruction (bottom). We deliberately ignore the slight amplitude modulations that can be noticed in the total original sound.

3.2.3. Test 3

Finally, we move to the sound segment heard in *Diamorphoses* from 4'20" to 4'51", marked by massively clustered glissandos, ascending and descending in the frequency range 1-7.3 kHz. In the piece, the clustered glissandos overlap with other sound materials (see the sonogram in Figure 8, top). Not to complicate matters, we decide to focus on the stream of ascending glissandos only. As the building block, we select a glissandoing bell distinctly heard at 1'45", whose spectrum has just two prominent frequency components (Figure 9, darker area in the sonogram).

The DME delay times are once again randomly regulated for maximal lack of periodical patterns. The playback head levels are themselves set to different random values, in the range 0 to -30 dB. Just like in the previous example, the first attempt does not give us a dense enough texture. So we submit the resultant sound again to the DME, randomly changing the delay times and the gain levels for all ten playback heads. In Figure 8 you see the sonogram of the original sound texture (top) and that of the sound texture we ended up with (bottom). Clearly, the latter is rid of the spectral striations relative to concomitant sounds. Yet, one can easily track down the similarity in the fabric of ascending glissandos.

Figure 7. *Diamorphoses*, excerpt 6'16" – 6'44" (top: original, bottom: reconstruction).

Figure 8. *Diamorphoses*, excerpt 4'20" – 4'51" (top: original, bottom: reconstruction).

Figure 9. *Diamorphoses*, the dark area highlights the snippet sound (phonogen-modulated bell) used as the base element for the example in Figure 8.

3.3. Discussion

Upon listening, there is a striking similarity between the sound materials under scrutiny and those we managed to create with the DME. All in all, disregarding the innumerable tiny differences in the detail of the audio signal, the sound streams we managed to obtain do appear as the output of the ‘same’ studio procedure by which Xenakis might have created his sound textures. They are way too ‘clean’, of course, in terms of audio quality. We could perhaps resort to the DME ‘virtual analog’ options to emulate analog pre-amplification stages in the signal, yielding a somewhat rougher and more ‘antique’ sounding effect. But that does not seem really necessary in order to fulfill our task and support our hypothesis, i.e. to ascertain that the morphophone may have been crucial in shaping up the ‘swarms of glissando’ of *Diamorphoses*.

Furthermore, it turns out that the reiteration of the morphophone process might have provided a reasonable and practical manner for increasing and perhaps even grading the density of the sound texture. No doubt, we cannot say anything precise concerning the choices Xenakis made in this regard. And yet, our tests strongly suggest that the reiteration of the morphophone processing might have provided him with a perhaps coarse but easily managed control over the density of the resultant sound textures. In the GRM studios of the time, no other technical strategy would have been as practical and economical in order to create these thicker strands or swarms of sounds. One can even dare say that, in fact, no other way existed to do that in any electroacoustic studio, at that time. After all, a single pass through the morphophone could only be compared with the mixing of up to ten tapes, each having sound materials of similar-but-slightly-different micro-temporal structure⁷.

⁷ In 1959, Xenakis found himself in a similar situation, as he worked on *Analogique B* [Di Scipio 2006, Di Scipio 2015, Di Scipio 2023]. The new compositional project (started in the Hermann Scherchen Studio, in Gravesano, Switzerland, and completed at GRM, in Paris) certainly laid on more solid and challenging theoretical grounds, namely on the notion of a quantum-based — or ‘granular’ — sound synthesis (as in [Gabor 1947]). However, in that particular circumstance Xenakis tried layering a great number of tapes, one by one, each featuring several short sine tones (‘acoustical quanta’ or ‘grains’). The task, albeit very ingeniously planned

3.4. Implications for music analysis

It should be noted that, across the whole duration of *Diamorphoses*, the sound textures Xenakis produced with the morphophone are presented at later or much later times after the elementary snippets they were derived from. There is a kind of hidden or internal development, not really continuing and gradual, but growing stepwise, presented across subsequent degrees of sonic complexity. Derivative of tiny bell sounds heard in early passages (in fact as early as 0'30"), the clustered glissandos gradually 'inflate' the complete musical structure, across a number of subsequent steps, eventually taking the center stage in the last minute or so. No other sound material in the piece goes through a similar musical treatment.

We suggest that Xenakis approached the morphophone as a device potentially generative of a transformational dynamic *in* and *through* sound, capable *to diamorphose* a reduced sound material into multi-layered musical constructs of astonishing sonorous qualities. Notwithstanding its serious technical problems, the morphophone worked for him as a compositional mechanism potentially productive of a structural musical plan, not of individual sound objects and sonorous effects. In that sense, *Diamorphoses* certainly represents a precursor of more mature developments in the context of (not only) Xenakis's electroacoustic and computer music [Di Scipio 1998, Di Scipio 2015, Di Scipio & Solomos 2025].

4. Conclusions

The research work described in this paper offers an attempt to study relevant aspects of the early electroacoustic repertoire through the modelling and reconstruction of sound materials and musical structures. The attempt took advantage of software resources purposefully designed (by one of the authors) to reconstruct the operations of an obsolete piece of technical apparatus, the morphophone, that has rarely received due attention [Scorranese 2025]. Broadly speaking, such effort connects with a strand of inquiry pivoting around the regeneration of musical constructs through modelling of pioneering, rare or even idiosyncratic devices or software (including research from a variety of musical and technical orientations, such as [Clarke 1998, Rizzo *et al.* 2002, Di Scipio 2002, Arcella & Silvestri 2012, Agostini & Bassanese 2014, Goldman *et al.* 2020, Mooney *et al.* 2022, Cortegiani *et al.* 2025]).

Similar efforts are not out of mere curiosity or techno-archeological fetishism: overall, they acknowledge the historically determined materiality of composing and consider the latter of relevance to music analysis and related scholarly work. Overall, they imply an 'ethnomethodologically informed' attitude in the study of creative practices born at the dawn of epoch-making upheavals, at the turn of late modernity and the contemporary [Di Scipio 1995].

As regards the research presented in this paper, we can draw more circumscribed conclusions. In the first place, our experiments with the DME show that peculiar sound materials featured in *Diamorphoses* were worked out with signal processing techniques that, in 1957, at GRM,

through various pre-mixing stages, eventually turned out to be very cumbersome and ended up hampering the creation of 'sound clouds' as dense as the composer aimed for.

could only be practiced with the morphophone, regardless of the serious technical problems hampering that unique device. This is indirect, deductive but empirically grounded evidence that the morphophone was indeed used in the making of *Diamorphoses* — or, more precisely, in the making of the dense sound textures that have been denoted as ‘swarms of glissandos’ and the likes.

Secondarily, we have seen that the ‘multiplicative’ or ‘accumulative’ function attributed to the morphophone in the GRM context, in the late 1950s, may have been understood by Xenakis as a resource to also exert some rough but effective control over the density of complex sound textures. It seems plausible that he proceeded in a kind of iterative way, either by submitting the output of earlier morphophone operations to subsequent morphophone operations, or by taking advantage of the feedback configurations feasible on the morphophone panel, or by removing the morphophone eraser head (overdub). It is impossible to say if any of these options might have helped him determine precise gradations of density, especially in consideration of the malfunctions and technical issues of the morphophone. Nevertheless, it seems clear that Xenakis saw in that unique device the potential for handling varied textural densities, as a dimension structural to the composition of *Diamorphoses*.

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